

Potassium Periodate as a Volumetric Reagent. Determination of Organic Derivatives of Hydrazine

Balwant Singh, S. S. Sabota, and Mohinder Paul Gupta

In presence of HCl, potassium periodate solution has been used as a volumetric reagent for the determination of nitroaminoguanidine, β -formylphenylhydrazine, β -acetylphenylhydrazine, adipic diphenylhydrazide, β -propionylphenylhydrazine, 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, *o*- & *p*-chlorobenzylidene semicarbazones, cinnamylidene semicarbazone, hydrazine sulphate, semicarbazide hydrochloride, benzylidene semicarbazone, 4-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride, benzalazine, and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene semicarbazone. In the visual titrations chloroform has been used as an indicator. In potentiometric titrations, platinum electrode has been used as an oxidation-reduction electrode, coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. At equivalence point there is a sharp jump in potential in each titration.

In these compounds each hydrazino group is quantitatively oxidised to nitrogen with potassium periodate by a four-electron change.

Singh *et al.* reported that potassium periodate reacted quantitatively with hydrazine sulphate involving the iodine monochloride (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 34) or iodine monobromide (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 9, 22), or iodine cyanide (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 143) end point. Singh and Singh (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 786) used potassium periodate in presence of a large excess of bromide in acid medium for the potentiometric titration of hydrazine sulphate. Berka and Zyka (*Chem. Listy*, 1956, 50, 314) determined isonicotinyll hydrazide, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide, and thiosemicarbazide by titrating them with 0.01M potassium periodate solution under different hydrochloric acid concentrations. Singh and Sabota (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1958, 17B, 386) determined phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, benzalazine, aminoguanidine, chloral hydrazine, semicarbazide hydrochloride, 4-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride, 3,4-methylenedioxy-, *p*-methoxy-, and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene semicarbazones in hydrochloric acid medium by titrating them with potassium periodate solutions with chloroform as indicator.

In the present study, potassium periodate has been used as an oxidant for the estimation of nitroaminoguanidine, β -formylphenylhydrazine, β -acetylphenylhydrazine, adipic diphenylhydrazide, β -propionylphenylhydrazine, 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, *o*- and *p*-chlorobenzylidene semicarbazones, cinnamylidene semicarbazone, hydrazine sulphate, semicarbazide hydrochloride, benzylidene semicarbazone, 4-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride, benzalazine, and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene semicarbazone, using iodine monochloride-chloroform as indicator in visual titrations. Equivalence point was also determined potentiometrically in most of the titrations.

In hydrochloric acid medium, each molecule of the organic derivatives of hydrazine is quantitatively oxidised with potassium periodate by a four-electron change per hydrazino group :

EXPERIMENTAL

Iodine Monochloride Method.—To a known amount of each substance, taken in a conical flask, water (40 c.c.), HCl (conc., 20 c.c.), and chloroform (5 c.c.) were added. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and titrated with a standard (0.0166M) potassium periodate solution. The reagent was added from a burette until the solution, which was coloured with iodine, became pale

yellow and chloroform layer acquired a purple colour due to iodine. The conical flask was stoppered and vigorously shaken during the titration. Addition of small volumes of potassium periodate was continued, shaking vigorously after each addition, until the chloroform layer became light pale yellow due to formation of iodine monochloride. The end point was very sharp.

TABLE I

Organic derivative of hydrazine.	Weight of hydrazine derivative by			
	Iodine monochloride method.		Potentiometric method.	
	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
$\text{HN}=\text{C} \begin{cases} \text{NH} \cdot \text{NH}_2 \\ \text{NH} \cdot \text{NO}_2 \end{cases}$	0.0122 g.	0.0122 g.	..	..
	0.0236	0.0237	..	..
HCONH.NH.C ₆ H ₅	0.0169 0.0357	0.0170 0.0357	0.0149 g. 0.0334	0.0149 g. 0.0332
CH ₃ CONH.NH.C ₆ H ₅	0.0194 0.0470	0.0193 0.0469	0.0126 0.0326	0.0126 0.0327
[C ₆ H ₅ NH.NHCO(CH ₂) ₄] ₂	0.0186 0.0488	0.0186 0.0490	..	..
CH ₃ CH ₂ CONH.NHC ₆ H ₅	0.0200 0.0486	0.0200 0.0484	..	..
(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ NH.NH ₂	0.0213 0.0513	0.0213 0.0515	..	..
<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH : N.NHCONH ₂	0.0212 0.0555	0.0211 0.0553	0.0213 0.0445	0.0214 0.0443
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH : N.NHCONH ₂	0.0236 0.0534	0.0236 0.0536	0.0205 0.0511	0.0204 0.0510
C ₆ H ₅ CH : CH.CH : N.NHCONH ₂	0.0212 0.0501	0.0211 0.0503	0.0196 0.0512	0.0195 0.0514
N ₂ H ₄ ·H ₂ SO ₄	0.0163 0.0390	0.0162 0.0392	0.0130 0.0388	0.0129 0.0386
NH ₂ CONH.NH ₂ ·HCl	..	..	0.0110 0.0223	0.0110 0.0221
C ₆ H ₅ CH : N.NHCONH ₂	..	..	0.0189 0.0374	0.0190 0.0372
C ₆ H ₅ NH.CONHNH ₂ ·HCl	..	..	0.0176 0.0325	0.0176 0.0326
(C ₆ H ₅ CH : N-) ₂	..	..	0.0213 0.0351	0.0214 0.0353
(OH)OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH : N.NHCONH ₂	..	..	0.0162 0.0454	0.0163 0.0456

In these titrations the normality of the solution with respect to HCl was kept between 3.0*N* and 3.8*N*, excepting in the cases of *β*-formylphenylhydrazine and adipic diphenylhydrazine where the acid normality was maintained between 5.0*N* and 7.0*N*. In the cases of nitroaminoguanidine and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, the acid normality was maintained between 1.7*N* and 2.2*N*. Several titrations were performed in each case. From the volume of the standard potassium periodate solution used, corresponding to the end point in each titration, the amount of each substance was calculated. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

Potentiometric Method.—A known amount of each substance was taken in a beaker; water (about 80 to 90 c.c.) and sufficient HCl (conc.) were added to keep the normality of the mixture with respect to the acid at 2*N*, excepting in the case of benzalazine where the acid normality was maintained at 3.5*N*. Chloroform (5 c.c.) was added to avoid volatilisation of iodine liberated during the reaction. The mixture was titrated potentiometrically with 0.0166 *M* potassium periodate solution.

A platinum wire electrode, immersed in the solution to be titrated, was used as an oxidation-reduction electrode and this was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The mixture was kept stirred with a mechanical stirrer during titration. Progress of the reaction was studied with a Mullard potentiometer. At the equivalence point a sharp jump in potential was observed in each titration. A series of potentiometric titrations was performed in each case with different amounts of the substance. The potentiometric titrations, one for each substance, are represented by the curves A to K in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

- A: 3-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzylidene semicarbazone.
- B: 4-Phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride.
- C: β -Formylphenylhydrazine.
- D: *o*-Chlorobenzylidene semicarbazone.
- E: Cinnamylidene semicarbazone.
- F: Benzalazine.
- G: Semicarbazide hydrochloride.
- H: β -Acetylphenylhydrazine.
- I: Benzylidene semicarbazone.
- J: *p*-Chlorobenzylidene semicarbazone.
- K: Hydrazine sulphate.

From the volume of the standard (0.0166 *M*) potassium periodate solution used, corresponding to the end point in each titration, the amount of each substance was calculated. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

The results recorded above show that the listed compounds can be determined volumetrically by titrating with a standard potassium periodate solution. All chemicals used in this investigation are of guaranteed purity.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PUNJAB UNIVERSITY,
CHANDIGARH-3.

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